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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anaphylaxis is a potentially life-threatening hypersensitivity reaction that may be triggered by immunoglobulin E (IgE) or non-IgE mediated mechanisms. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are known to provoke anaphylaxis via direct mast cell activation, even in previously undiagnosed patients.

Case Presentation: We report a case of a 17-year-old adolescent male who developed anaphylaxis following ibuprofen ingestion. The clinical diagnosis was supported despite a normal serum tryptase level, and the patient was treated successfully with intramuscular adrenaline.

Conclusion: This case emphasizes the importance of early recognition, prompt treatment, and long-term individualized management in adolescents.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Adolescent, anaphylaxis, epinephrine, ibuprofen, NSAIDs

INTRODUCTION

Anaphylaxis is an acute, life-threatening systemic hypersensitivity reaction caused by the sudden release of mediators from mast cells and basophils (Turner et al., 2019). The majority of anaphylactic reactions are mediated by immunoglobulin E (IgE), with the most frequent triggers being foods, medications, and insect stings (Simons et al., 2015). However, some cases of anaphylaxis may occur via non-IgE-mediated mechanisms. Notably, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) can induce angioedema and anaphylaxis through direct activation of mast cells (Kemp et al., 2023).

The diagnosis of anaphylaxis is primarily clinical, based on the acute onset of skin and/or mucosal symptoms (such as urticaria or angioedema), along with at least one systemic involvement.

These systemic findings may include:

- Gastrointestinal system (GI): crampy abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea
- Respiratory system: dyspnea, wheezing, laryngeal edema, stridor, hypoxia
- Cardiovascular system: end-organ damage, tachycardia, hypotension, syncope

In patients with previously identified allergies, the presence of systemic signs such as hypotension, bronchospasm, or laryngeal edema -even in the absence of cutaneous findings- is sufficient to support the

diagnosis of anaphylaxis (Muraro et al., 2014). The first and most critical step in anaphylaxis treatment is intramuscular epinephrine administration, and early intervention significantly affects patient outcomes. Long-term management of anaphylaxis includes allergen avoidance, specialist follow-up, and the prescription of an epinephrine auto-injector (Kemp et al., 2023).

This case report presents a 17-year-old adolescent who developed anaphylaxis following ibuprofen intake and had a previous history of similar reactions.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 17-year-old male presented to the emergency department (ED) with symptoms of upper respiratory tract infection and was prescribed an over-the-counter cold remedy containing ibuprofen. Approximately 30 minutes after ingesting the medication, the patient developed facial and lip angioedema and returned to the ED (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Facial and lip angioedema observed at initial emergency department presentation

Upon presentation, his vital signs were stable: blood pressure 120/70 mmHg and heart rate 110 bpm. Physical examination revealed no uvular edema, and breath sounds were normal. Initial treatment included 40 mg of intravenous pheniramine and 60 mg of prednisolone. However, within 10 minutes, the patient reported a sensation of throat tightness. Given the clinical presentation, the diagnostic criteria for anaphylaxis were met, and 0.5 mg of intramuscular adrenaline was promptly administered into the anterolateral thigh. Symptoms improved markedly following adrenaline administration (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2

Clinical appearance at the 10th minute following intramuscular adrenaline administration

Figure 3

Patient's condition at the fifth hour of clinical observation

In light of the risk of biphasic anaphylaxis, the patient was admitted to the pediatric unit for close observation with continuous cardiac monitoring. During follow-up, vital signs remained stable, and laboratory analysis revealed a serum tryptase level of 6.60 ng/mL. Further history revealed a prior occurrence of similar symptoms after NSAID intake. Following full resolution of symptoms, the patient was discharged after 24 hours with a referral to the pediatric allergy and immunology clinic.

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's legal guardian.

DISCUSSION

This case highlights that NSAIDs can trigger anaphylaxis through non-IgE-mediated pathways. These drugs are widely used and often accessible without a prescription, particularly among adolescents. While NSAIDs inhibit cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes to reduce inflammation, they can also destabilize mast cells and promote degranulation, leading to potentially life-threatening reactions in sensitized individuals (Kemp et al., 2023).

Although laboratory tests such as serum tryptase may support the diagnosis, anaphylaxis remains a clinical diagnosis. Tryptase is typically elevated in IgE-mediated reactions but may remain normal in non-IgE-mediated cases. Thus, a normal tryptase level does not rule out the diagnosis. In this case, despite normal tryptase, the clinical findings warranted urgent intervention.

Timely administration of intramuscular adrenaline is critical for effective anaphylaxis management. Patients should be monitored for at least 4–6 hours due to the risk of biphasic reactions; in high-risk cases, observation up to 24 hours is recommended (Tole & Lieberman, 2007).

Awareness of anaphylaxis tends to be limited among adolescents, who may underestimate the clinical significance of previous mild reactions or drug exposures. Comprehensive history-taking and education on the proper use of epinephrine auto-injectors are essential for both patients and caregivers to prevent recurrence (Simons et al., 2015).

NSAID-induced anaphylaxis is not uncommon and must be considered in pediatric and adolescent patients presenting with acute allergic reactions. The diagnosis of anaphylaxis is primarily clinical, and immediate administration of epinephrine is lifesaving. This case underscores the importance of early recognition, rapid intervention, and individualized long-term management. In individuals with a documented history of hypersensitivity reactions, repeated exposure may lead to severe consequences; therefore, management plans should be carefully tailored to mitigate future risk and prevent recurrence.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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